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Karma Yoga Concept in Shrimad Bhagavad Gita: A Conceptual Frame Development

Anjali Prabhakar¹ and Paran Gowda²

Abstract

Karma Yoga in Bhagavad Gita is the core principle of action and it projects the spiritual values of India. The study develops a conceptual frame based on 700 verses from 18 chapters. The need of the conceptual frame arises due to lack of scientific understanding of Gita. To demonstrate the frame, a sample size of 500 participants is selected. A psychometric analysis of 19 items may be developed after cognitive interviews. The results show that a karma yoga frame may be suitable for measuring the duty orientation. The CVI and alpha are found to be 0.92 and 0.72.

Key words

Karma yoga; Scale development; Human excellence; Reference Frame

1. Introduction

Mukherjee, et al (2018) explains the nomenclature of the term “Karma Yoga” (KY), a Sanskrit word, which comes from “Kri”, it means “To-Do” ; all actions performed by humans are “Karma” . This term KY is explained in great detail in the Indian philosophical text book- Bhagavad Gita. Mullah and Krishnan (2006), explains KY with 3-dimensions having duty orientation, equanimity and absence of desire for rewards expected from action.

Tenneti and Tenneti (2017), proves that the effectiveness of the work depends not only on the external motivating factors like incentives but it is connected to the ‘inner world ‘of the person, therefore Karma Yoga can be called Science of Human Excellence. Pati.et al (2017) Karma

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yoga is the path of self-realisation. Mulla, et al (2018), describes KY as a novel explanation for moral behaviour beyond the theories of self-interest. Krishnan and Mulla (2022) explains a distinct motivation for action, based on one's duty toward others. Umashankar and Charitra (2021), tries to exemplify commonalities among these dimensions and their applicability in achieving personal transformation. Mullah and Krishnan (2011) assess the extent of Karma-Yoga orientation in a respondent. Rastogi & Pati's (2015) developed a conceptualization frame of Karma Yoga and established an instrument of 6- item Karma Yoga Instrument (KYI-6). Preliminary evidence regarding convergent validity, discriminant validity, validity, and internal consistency of the measure is provided. Mullah and Krishnan (2009) finds that a leader's duty-orientation was related to a leader's charisma and inspirational motivation. Pradhan (2013) explores the relationship between karma-yoga (spirit at work) and a set of job attitudes. Jeste and Vahia (2008), compare conceptualization of wisdom in the Gita with that apparent differences include an emphasis on control over desires and renunciation of materialistic pleasures. Muppudathi and Krishnan (2021), focuses on increasing the frequency of idealised influence attributed, idealised influence behaviour, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation of managers results in making the employees more karma-yoga oriented. Mukherjee and Singha (2018), Karma yoga philosophy gives vision from Indian philosophy on today's business problems of job attitudes.

Methodology

Scale development is a systematic process that is carried out at different stages of analysis. De Vellis (2016) recommends a ratio of 1:10 or 1:15 or 1:20 as an ideal sample size. Pasqual L scale development for the present study was accomplished in three stages namely item generation, theoretical analysis, and psychometric analysis. In the study of Singh 2018, data was gathered from religious transmission among the 18-40 year old population, which used a variety of research methods including interviews, participant observation, focus groups and an online survey. In the same way in the present study, data was collected through online mode due to Covid-19.

Procedure of scale development

Karma yoga scale

Karma yoga scale development is a systematic process that is carried out at different stages of analysis. Following recommendations of DeVellis RF and Pasquali L scale development for the present study was accomplished in three stages viz; item generation, theoretical analysis and psychometric analysis.

Item Generation:

The Content domain was specified through review of literature related to karma yoga orientation towards duty as specified in yoga philosophy. Among 18 chapters of Bhagavad Gita, the karma yoga human excellence conceptual model (Fig.1) that relates beliefs with social health and wellbeing was considered to specify the content domain. The model comprises KYS of 19 items. The researcher considered all 19 items as KY related constructs for scale development. Item pool generation provides a conceptual endorsement for the initial item pool of 37 items. The present research employed a combination of deductive and inductive methods of initial item pool generation. The researchers reviewed literature related to the Health Benefit Model, Human excellence and social health behaviour to acquire basic comprehension about the concept and take leads for developing constructs and items. The researchers also interacted with experts in the fields of yoga science and obtained qualitative information regarding the content domains and objective of the research. The information was analyzed and related with the concept of KY and human excellence to generate pool initial items. As a result, 19 items were developed. Items worded negatively for the construct were reverse coded and scored. Following the recommendations by parameters such simplicity, clarity, specificity, capability to ensure variability of response and freeness from bias of the items were carefully considered while drafting the items.

Theoretical analysis

Content validity

Content validity of the initial items was assessed to make sure that the items are representative of the identified construct i.e.KY towards

human excellence. The researchers, in order to assess content validity of the initial items, clearly defined the conceptual framework of KY towards human excellence by undertaking a thorough literature review and seeking expert opinion. The expert panel comprised 5 experts; one Vedic Philosophy expert from Texas, USA, and an expert in Bhagavad Gita philosophy from Bangalore another expert in Indian philosophy. The experts assessed the relevance of items in relation to the content domain applying a tool namely Content Validity Index (CVI) developed by Waltz. The experts rated each item against a four-point scale (1=Not relevant, 2=somewhat relevant, 3=Quite relevant and 4=highly relevant). A score of 3 or 4 indicates that the content represented by each item was considered valid and in harmony with the theory that is being measured and they are retained. The items which received score 1 or 2 were rejected from the scale indicating the theoretically or practically irrelevant questions or any ambiguous items that apparently repeated the essential content of other items.

Face validity

The visual appearance of the tool is tested by its readability and feasibility with 10 individuals. The respondents were asked to judge the user-friendliness of the tool. Feedback from the respondents was incorporated to improve the tool. This process was helpful to assess ambiguity and skewness i.e. respondents providing very similar answers to all the items.

Psychometric analysis:

The psychometric analysis involves a number of quantitative techniques to test construct validity and reliability of the scale. Construct validity according to Posak is the quantity to which interpretation can be meaningfully constructed from the observed scores to the hypothetical constructs about which the observations are meant to hold information. In addition to construct validity, convergent validity, criterion validity and discriminate validity of the scale were tested quantitatively. DeVellis (2016) strongly recommends the combined use of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to achieve consistent results of the psychometric indices. Hence, these validity tests were done by

using EFA and CFA. Reliability, a quantification method producing the consistent results on recurring examinations as measured in terms of indicators namely Cronbach alpha, Correlation coefficients, composite reliability and average variance extraction. Concurrent validity was assessed by calculating the correlation between the scores of the present scale and relate with other KY scales.

Data collection and analysis:

In this study the scale was with five options ranging from 'strongly disagree' (score 1) to 'strongly agree' (score 5). Each of the items in the scale is an agreement statement on the five point Likert scale, which is a quantitative technique meant for measuring psychological variables like attitude, perception, anxiety, stress, beliefs etc. All the items in the scale were positively stated to the outcome variable human excellence. The summated score of all the items was treated as the quantifiable measure of the construct and it was considered for all quantitative analytical purposes. All items included in the Likert scale were considered as continuous variables. The scale was prepared in English and Hindi to facilitate respondents' comprehension over the statements. The questionnaire was filled by the respondents. Factors are extracted and a factor structure including the correlation between the factors is proposed by EFA. The proposed factor structure is hypothesised and tested in CFA. If the statistical results fit with the hypothesised model the researcher can conclude that the factor structure is valid. Hence, the study evaluated the scale using both EFA and CFA. IBM SPSS 25 software version was used to calculate descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, EFA by using IBM SPSS Amos 25 software. Construct validity was assessed by computing model fitness indices namely p value of Chi square, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, CFI, TLI, NFI and Chisq / df which were the outputs of confirmatory factor analysis. Discriminate validity was examined by measuring the level of redundancy of items through Modification Indices (MI).

Results and Discussion

All the above philosophical studies show the relationship between the constructs of Karma Yoga scale from Gita as well as from other philosophical texts. The present KY-19 scale is discussed with reference

to the scales that were developed from 2003 to 2022

It may be seen in Fig. 1 that KY questionnaire development two ways has started from 2003 to 2022. As observed, there is a fluctuating behaviour of items (factors) development. The maximum numbers of items are proposed in the year 2022 by Anjali & Paran. The proposed increase in numbers of items may be due to the fact that the KY concept is complex and to make it simplified, it was felt that there is a need for more number of questions. So, all 18 chapters in this paper, we proposed 36 no. of KY verses from Bhagavad Gita (Prabhupada, 2015). We developed 36 questions, initially. Mulla and Krishnan (2014) developed other authors like Mulla and other concepts are based on Gita but weak correlation and reliability exists between the items. And also in their research paper, no definite conclusion was drawn from their conceptual frame of references. Rastogi (2020) Karma-Yoga in accordance with Rastogi and Pati's (2015) conceptualisation, which follows a conceptual and methodological critique of extant operationalization. We report results from three studies using distinct samples. Preliminary evidence on convergent validity, discriminant validity, homological validity, and internal consistency of the proposed instrument is provided.

As seen from Fig. 2, the number of items in the KY scale development from 2003 to 2022 is increasing and decreasing. The first scale by Narayanan and Krishnan (2003) has an alpha value of 0.7 but without conceptual frame and expert validation. It can be observed that most alpha values reported reliability below 0.70. Four of subscale (in separated studies) reported reliability below 0.60. However, the author had not incorporated suitable steps to validate the scale. Third, owing to the limited choices of reliable and valid measures, researchers prefer to use the instrument developed by Mulla and Krishnan (2006), which is a precursor to the warning by Cook and Campbell (1976) about the potential under representation of constructs in research. Hence, there is a pronounced need for psychometrically robust additional measures for Karma Yoga, to facilitate triangulation (triangulation (Cook & Campbell, 1976) and high construct validity (Messick, 1995). The scale proposed in the present study, has both content validity index of 0.92 and internal reliability value of 0.70.

6. Conclusions

Based on the above qualitative and quantitative studies of KY verses from 18 chapters of Gita, we proposed a relative reference

frame for the studies. The psychological instrument proposes 19 statements under 3 subdomains of duty, desire and human excellence of KY.

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